

Paper 2

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SELF HELP GROUPS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANGALORE TALUK

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Abstract:

India, our country, is well known for its cultural heritage, civilization, religion and its geographical features. We proudly portray our nation as “Bharat-Mata” and raise slogans in praise of our unity, integrity and dignity. While doing so, we fail to realise that “Bharat-Mata” means mother to every Indian. But in India, women are considered weak compared to men. Right from the beginning women were considered as knowledge-less creatures, which were kept inside the kitchen to do all the household chores. She was never allowed to indulge in social and political affairs of the society. But today, the status of the women is at a high level not only in the family but also in the business area compared to men. Women, today, are not only confined to domestic chores like upbringing of children but they also form an integral part of the society and make a significant contribution to the development of the nation. Primarily, now women are dominant as much as men they become equal to men in every area. Thanks to universal declaration of human rights to receive inheritance, divorce or express themselves liberally. Secondly, when we look at the business field, we see the profile of working, producing women today. They also gained dignity in the business area today. It is possible to see women in every field just because of the women empowerment programme. This research is undertaken to learn about the women empowerment program conducted by the Self-Help Groups and to know how they benefit women members socially and economically.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Self-Help Groups, Members & Financial Support.

1. INTRODUCTION

India, our nation, is well-known for its cultural heritage, economy, religion and geographical characteristics. We are proud to depict our country as “Bharat-Mata” and raise slogans to praise our unity, honour and dignity. In doing so, we fail to realise that for every Indian, “Bharat-Mata” means mother. But in India, compared to men, women are considered weak. From the beginning, women were treated as knowledge-less beings that were kept in the kitchen to do all the household chores. She was never allowed to participate in society’s social and political affairs. Yet today, not only in the home, but also in the business area, women’s status is high compared to men. Women today are not only confined to domestic tasks such as children upbringing, they are also an integral part of society and make a significant contribution

to the nation's growth. First and foremost, women are now as dominant as men in every field as they become equal to men. Thanks to universal human rights declaration to obtain property, divorce and express themselves in a progressive manner. Second, we see the profile of employed, creating women today, as we look at the field of business. They have also earned credibility in today's business environment. Only because of women's empowerment program can women be seen in any field.

2. WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Essentially, this creates an environment in the simplest terms in which women can make independent decisions about their personal development and shine as partners in society. According to Swami Vivekananda, "There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved. It is not possible for a bird, to fly on one wing". It the 1985 International Women's Conference in Nairobi, which described women's empowerment as a philosophy, it was presented as a redistribution of social power and control of resources for women. Women Empowerment in India, therefore, aims primarily to enhance their social functioning through a quantitative and qualitative change, especially in the field of education, health and employment.

3. SELF-HELP GROUPS

Self-Help Organisations are informal voluntary networks of people from the same socio-economic background to solve their common problems. Methods followed by Self-Help Groups to Empower the Women:

- To sensitise target area women for the end of the self-help group and their importance in their empowerment process
- To build group feeling between them
- Boost women's innovative decision-making
- Provide them with appropriate training on how to manage their business, how to use the funds raised in self-help groups, how to use their loans for productive purposes.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has been designed with the following objectives-

- To study the operating system of Self-Help Groups for the mobilization, delivery and management of funds.
- To know the women empowerment programme conducted by the Self-Help Groups.
- To evaluate economic and social benefits obtained by members since entering SHGs.
- To measure the satisfaction level of the beneficiaries of Self-Help Groups.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study undertaken includes both primary and secondary data. The primary data is first-hand information collected for the purpose of survey. The information for this study is collected through questionnaire. The structured questionnaire was distributed to respondents in Mangalore Taluk. The secondary data is obtained from various journals, books, magazines and a few web sites. The data collected through the questionnaire was put together in the form of tables and analysed, simple percentage method is used for the analysis.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Majority of respondents (i.e.,60%) were joined SHG for the reason of availing loan & remaining 40% were joined to save money. As per my study all the respondents were satisfied

by joining SHG. Out of 50 respondents' only 32 respondents' availed loan provided by SHG. Among them 17 respondents (i.e., 53%) were availed loan for domestic expenditure & remaining 15 respondents (i.e., 47%) were availed loan for Self-Employment (like textile shop, sole trading concern, etc). Out of 32 respondents 11 respondents (i.e., 35%) were availed a loan of below Rs. 10000, 17 respondents (i.e., 53%) were availed loan between Rs.10000-25000, 2 respondents (i.e., 6%) were availed loan of Rs.26000-50000 & remaining 2 respondents (i.e.,6%) were availed more than Rs.50000. The study reveals that 100% of respondents agreed that they get loan at low rate of interest in SHG. 100% of respondents were became financially empowered after joining SHG. The study concerned that financial status of women empowered after becoming member of SHG. Out of 50 respondents 46% respondents were undergone training given by SHG& remaining 54% were not undergone any form of training. Training was about establishing their own business, tailoring classes, etc. Out of 50 respondents 64% were responded that they are getting social recognition, very much after joining SHG & remaining 36% were not getting that much social recognition.

7. FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

Most of the respondents joining SHG for availing loan. In study region, maximum number of respondents availed loan amount of Rs.10000-Rs.25000. All the respondents opinion is that loan is given at low rate of interest. All the respondents become financially independent after joining SHG. Majority of respondents getting social recognition after joining SHG and they gained confidence in doing their work on their own after joining SHG. The bank should advance adequate credit to the SHG members according to their needs. The office bearers managing the group should be given nominal financial benefits, which will enable them to be more involved in the activities of the group. It is suggested that training on innovative economic activities by using the resources in & around the taluk may be given to the members. The incentives may be given for prompt repayment of loan. This will draw the attention of the groups to repay the loan.

8. CONCLUSION

The modern era has created many obstacles that have put many nations experiencing change, transcending their tradition and culture. New issues must be tackled in order to bring about our nation's social and economic development. Women's empowerment by self-help groups is the most significant one. SHG has undeniably started to make a significant contribution to alleviating poverty and empowering the vulnerable, particularly women in rural areas. Women are the vital infrastructure and their inclusion will accelerate the speed of social development. The sure way to contribute to economic growth and social development is to invest in women's skills and inspire them to achieve choices and opportunities. The atmosphere of rural women not only leads to helping different groups of women and children, but also to help the facilities and community as a whole. This research is an effort to examine member's socio-economic development and women's success in SHG. SHG's performance has been great. As a member of SHG, the lower numbers of women are positively affected. Women's involvement in this scheme is discovering inner and building capability. If the above suggestions are made by the relevant authorities, the study will further improve the status of women in the Mangalore taluk.

REFERENCE

1. Dr.Thresiamma Varghese (2011), Women Empowerment in Oman: A study based on Women Empowerment Index, *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*, 2(2).
2. Dr.M.R.Singariya (2014), Dr B R Ambedkar and Women Empowerment in India, *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*,2(1), pp. 01-04.
3. Soumitro Chakravarty, Anant Kumar, Amar Nath Jha(2013). 'Women's Empowerment in India: Issues, Challenges and Future Directions', *International Review of Social Science and Humanities*,5(1), pp. 154-163
4. Nripendra Kishore Mishra, Tulika Tripathi (2011). 'Conceptualising Women's Agency, Autonomy and Empowerment', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46(11), pp. 58-65
5. Goswami, L. (2013). 'Education for Women Empowerment', *Abhibyakti: Annual Journal*, 1, 17-18.
6. Kadam, R. N. (2012). 'Empowerment of Women in India- An Attempt to Fill the Gender Gap', *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2(6), 11-13.
7. Beteta, K.C. (2006): "What is Missing in Measures of Women's Empowerment?", *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 7(2), pp.221-241.
8. Dr. Rashmi Rani Agnihotri H.R and 2Dr. Malipatil, K.S.(2017). 'A STUDY ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT SCHEMES IN INDIA', *International Journal of Development Research*, 7(8), pp.14301-14308.
9. Manav Aggarwal (2014), 'A STUDY ON CHALLENGE FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT', *Abhinav National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, 3(5).
10. Malika, S., & Courtney, K. (2011). 'Higher Education and Women's Empowerment in Pakistan', *Gender and Education*, Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 29-45.
11. Sonowal, M. K. (2013). 'Impact of Education in Women Empowerment: A Case Study of SC and ST women of Sonitpur District, Assam'. *IJCAES Special Issue on Basic, Applied and Social* , Vol. 3.
12. Taxak, D. P. (2013). 'Women Empowerment Through Higher Education', *International Indexed & Refereed Research Journal* , 4;(4).